

Supplementary information

Leveraging image processing techniques to visualize sub-cellular domains in optical photothermal infrared imaging

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SI 1 Spectral ranges of MIRcat-QCT-z

	Chip 1	Chip 2	Chip 3	Chip 4
Range / cm^{-1}	2936-2347	1797-1347	1505-1195	1271-930

Table 1 Spectral ranges of the MIRcat-QCT-z

SI 2 Effect of different filters

Figure 1 shows the effect of the filters on the selected pixels and the resulting convex hull for each of the tested filters.

Figure 1 Threshold filters and resulting masks. a) brightfield image, b) transmission image, c) complement of the transmission image, d) and g): image after Otsu filtering and resulting mask; e) and h) image after Li filtering and resulting mask; f) and i): image after Sauvola filtering and resulting mask.